

Development of Alternative Diesel Oxidation Catalysts

Henrik Teglberg¹

Supervisors: Prof. Anker Degn Jensen², Prof. Weigang Lin^{2,3},
Postdoc Martin Høj², PhD Thomas Klint Hansen²

¹SDC – Sino Danish Center for Education and Research

²DTU – Chemical and Biochemical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark

³IPE – Institute of Process Engineering, Chinese Academy of Sciences

INTRODUCTION

Emissions, smog and pollutants are under strict regulation worldwide, which requires the manufacturers of emitting equipment to take precautionary steps to meet emission regulation standards. For diesel engines, a series of catalytic units is used to treat the exhaust gas, see figure 1. An important unit in the diesel exhaust aftertreatment system is the Diesel Oxidation Catalyst (DOC), which oxidizes CO and unburnt hydrocarbons to CO₂. The DOC is commonly a 1% platinum on aluminum oxide (1wt.% Pt/Al₂O₃), possibly with some Palladium. The use of noble metals makes the DOC an expensive aftertreatment component. An effective/efficient use of the noble metals is therefore important for the development of the DOC both in terms of effectiveness, economy and environmental aspect.

Figure 1: An example of the standard diesel exhaust aftertreatment system¹.

¹(R. M. Heck, R. J. Farrauto, and S. T. Gulati, Catalytic air pollution control: commercial technology. John Wiley & Sons, 2012.)

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

To get a better understanding on the effects of Pt dispersion, a series of 1 wt.% Pt/Al₂O₃ catalysts have been developed with varying Pt particle sizes to analyze the CO oxidation. The catalysts were prepared by varying calcination atmosphere and/or subsequent aging with varied duration and temperature. The prepared catalysts were tested for CO oxidation in a gas flow reactor for varying temperatures and in humid environment.

RESULTS

Preliminary results show that lower dispersion (25%) can be achieved by using a pretreatment with higher temperatures (750°C) and longer exposure time (12-48 hours) in nitrogen gas. If higher dispersion is desired it is recommended to use lower temperatures (550°C) and using simulated atmosphere consisting of nitrogen, oxygen(10%) and water (3%). All versions obtained a desired full conversion from CO to CO₂ with varying light-off temperatures favoring a high pretreatment temperature.